

LAGUERRE COLLECTION METHOD TO SOLVE HIGH-ORDER LINEAR SINGULAR DIFFERENTIAL DIFFERENCE EQUATIONS

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Article Info

Oral Presentation

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14497079

Keywords

Numerical Solutions,
Laguerre Polynomials
Laguerre Collection Method,
Collection Points.

Abstract

Numerical solutions are approximate solutions to higher-order differential equations. These solutions are frequently employed in situations where analytical answers are difficult or impossible to find. Numerical methods for differential equations refer to techniques for obtaining numerical approximations of differential equations (DEs). This paper presents a numerical approach for obtaining an approximate solution to higher-order differential equations. The Laguerre Collection approach has been proposed for several types of differential equations. The Laguerre Polynomial was used to demonstrate the Laguerre collocation method for solving higher-order differential equations. The Laguerre collection method works by computing the coefficients in the Laguerre expansion of a high-order differential equation solution. The proposed method may convert many sorts of problems into algebraic equations by using truncated Laguerre series solutions, matrix operations, and collection points. The unknown Laguerre coefficients were calculated by solving the system of equations. Changes have been made for each form of differential equation. Numerical experiments were used to assess the method's accuracy and efficiency. The efficacy of this method was compared to the Bessel Collection Method. The results of Numerical Illustrations were calculated using the MATLAB R2020b computer software.

1. Introduction

The technology of today has made life easier. Everything in this technological age is dependent on machines. Computers, robotics, artificial intelligence, contemporary defense weapons, amusement games, and weather forecasts all play significant roles in human daily life [7], [8], [3] and [12]. Differential equations are utilized to solve the models of all these technology-based objects. A differential equation is an equation that involves the derivative of a function. The differential equations' order is referred to as the derivative's order. Differential equations are used to simulate character movement in games and animated videos, offer the shape, inside, and exterior design of robots, and comprehend computer hardware related to applied physics and electrical engineering challenges. [6] Singular boundary value problems occur in many models of non-Newtonian fluid dynamics, mathematical physics, astrophysics, etc. For example, the theory of the internal structure of stars, clusters of galaxies, the thermal behavior of a spherical cloud of gas acting under the

mutual attraction of its molecules, and theories of thermionic currents are modeled using singular differential-difference equations.

In this study, approximation solutions of Singular boundary value problems are obtained by using Laguerre Collection Method which is based on Laguerre Polynomials. The higher-order singular differential-difference equations is represented as [9]

$$\sum_{j=0}^J \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{P_{jk}(x)}{x(x-c)} y^{(k)}(\alpha_{jk}x + \beta_{jk}) = g(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq c \quad (1)$$

with the mixed boundary conditions

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} [a_{ik}y^{(k)}(0) + c_{ik}y^{(k)}(c)] = \lambda_i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, m-1 \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha_{jk}, \beta_{jk}, a_{ik}, c_{ik}$ and λ_i are constants, $y^{(0)}(x) = y(x)$ is an unknown function, the functions $P_{jk}(n), g(x) \in C(0, c)$ and also, the functions $P_{jk}(x), g(x)$ defined on $x = 0$ and $x = c$.

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2. Fundamental Matrix Relations

A numerical method in order to solve the pantograph equation with proportional delay under mixed conditions. The approach was based on first taking the functions in the differential-difference equations of the truncated Boubaker series and then substituting their matrix forms into the equation. The outcome matrix equation was then resolved and approximately the unknown Boubaker coefficients were found. In terms of Boubaker polynomials, the solution was obtained. The results obtained were calculated by the defined outcomes [1].

High-order linear singular differential-difference equations (SDDEs) is represented as:

$$\sum_{j=0}^J \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{P_{jk}(x)}{x(x-c)} y^{(k)} (\alpha_{jk}x + \beta_{jk}) = g(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq c \quad (3)$$

with the mixed boundary conditions

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} [a_{ik}y^{(k)}(0) + c_{ik}y^{(k)}(c)] = \lambda_i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, m-1 \quad (4)$$

where $(\alpha_{jk}, \beta_{jk}, a_{ik}, c_{ik})$ and (λ_i) are constants, $(y^{(0)}(x) = y(x))$ is an unknown function, the functions $P_{jk}(n), g(x) \in C(0, c)$, and also, the functions $P_{jk}(x), g(x)$ are defined on $x = 0$ and $x = c$.

Differential Transform Method to solve any kind and order of differential equations. Two linear and one non-linear differential equations have been solved, and solutions have been obtained in sequence. Numerical findings have shown that DTM is a reliable approach for solving differential equations [2].

In this study, the approximate solution is found by using the truncated Laguerre Collection Method based on Laguerre Polynomials. The series form for the solution of differential equations is defined as: [4]

$$y(x) = \sum_{n=0}^N c_n \mathcal{L}_n(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

where N is any positive integer, C_n are unknown Laguerre coefficients, and $\mathcal{L}_N(x)$ are Laguerre series defined as:

The Laguerre polynomial is expressed as

$$\mathcal{L}_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \binom{n}{k} x^k, \quad n \in N, \quad 0 \leq t < \infty. \quad (6)$$

The matrix form of the series is given as [10]

$$y(x) = \mathbf{L}(x)\mathbf{C} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\mathbf{L}(x) = [\mathcal{L}_0(x) \quad \mathcal{L}_1(x) \quad \mathcal{L}_2(x) \quad \mathcal{L}_3(x) \quad \dots \quad \mathcal{L}_N(x)]$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} c_0 \\ c_1 \\ c_2 \\ c_3 \\ \vdots \\ c_N \end{bmatrix}$$

The series $\mathbf{L}(x)$ in matrix form is expressed as [5]

$$\mathbf{L}(x) = \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{K}^T, \quad (8)$$

where $(\mathbf{X}(x))$ and (\mathbf{K}) are defined as:

$$\mathbf{X}(x) = [1 \quad x^1 \quad x^2 \quad x^3 \quad \dots \quad x^N] \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1/2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & -N & -N/2! & \dots & (-1)^N/N! \end{bmatrix}$$

The relation between Eq. (8) and Eq. (9) is given as:

$$y(x) = \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{K}^T\mathbf{C} \quad (10)$$

The relation between the $\mathbf{X}(x)$

and its derivatives is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}^{(1)}(x) &= \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{D}^T, \\ \mathbf{X}^{(2)}(x) &= \mathbf{X}(x)(\mathbf{D}^T)^2, \dots, \\ \mathbf{X}^{(k)}(x) &= \mathbf{X}(x)(\mathbf{D}^T)^k. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{D} is a matrix of coefficients and is defined as:

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 3 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & N \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

By using (11), the matrix relation for $y^{(1)}(x)$ is defined as:

$$y^{(1)}(x) = \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{D}^T\mathbf{K}^T\mathbf{C}, \quad (12)$$

$$y^{(2)}(x) = \mathbf{X}(x)(\mathbf{D}^T)^2\mathbf{K}^T\mathbf{C}, \quad (13)$$

and similarly,

$$y^{(k)}(x) = \mathbf{X}(x)(\mathbf{D}^T)^k\mathbf{K}^T\mathbf{C} \quad (14)$$

Using $x \rightarrow \alpha_{jk} + \beta_{jk}$ in (7)

$$y^{(k)}(\alpha_{jk} + \beta_{jk}) = \mathbf{X}(\alpha_{jk} + \beta_{jk})(\mathbf{D}^T)^k\mathbf{K}^T\mathbf{C}. \quad (15)$$

The relation between matrix $\mathbf{X}(x)$ and $\mathbf{X}(\alpha_{jk} + \beta_{jk})$ is defined as:

$$\mathbf{X}(\alpha_{jk} + \beta_{jk}) = \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{D}(\alpha_{jk}, \beta_{jk}) \quad (16)$$

$\mathbf{D}(\alpha_{jk}, \beta_{jk})$ matrix is defined as:

For $\alpha_{jk} \neq$ and $\beta_{jk} \neq$:

$$= \begin{bmatrix} (\alpha_{jk})^0 (\beta_{jk})^0 \binom{0}{0} & (\alpha_{jk})^0 (\beta_{jk})^1 \binom{1}{0} & \dots & (\alpha_{jk})^0 (\beta_{jk})^N \binom{N}{0} \\ 0 & (\alpha_{jk})^1 (\beta_{jk})^0 \binom{1}{1} & \dots & (\alpha_{jk})^1 (\beta_{jk})^{N-1} \binom{N}{1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & (\alpha_{jk})^N (\beta_{jk})^0 \binom{N}{N} \end{bmatrix}$$

For $\alpha_{jk} \neq$ and $\beta_{jk} =$:

$$\mathbf{D}_{(\alpha_{jk}0)} = \begin{bmatrix} (\alpha_{jk})^0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & (\alpha_{jk})^1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & (\alpha_{jk})^N \end{bmatrix}$$

Relation between (15) and (16) is defined as:

$$y^{(k)}(\alpha_{jk} + \beta_{jk}) = \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{D}(\alpha_{jk}, \beta_{jk})(\mathbf{D}^T)^{kK^{TC}}, \quad (17)$$

Using (17) in (1):

$$\sum_{j=0}^J \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{P_{jk}(x)}{x(x-c)} \mathbf{X}(x)\mathbf{D}(\alpha_{jk}, \beta_{jk})(\mathbf{D}^T)^{kK^{TC}} = g(x). \quad (18)$$

Main Results

Substitute the collection points defined by

$$x_i = \frac{c}{N}i, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Now,

$$\sum_{j=0}^J \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{P_{jk}(x_i)}{x_i(x_i-c)} \mathbf{X}(x_i)\mathbf{D}(\alpha_{jk}, \beta_{jk})(\mathbf{D}^T)^{kK^{TC}} = g(x_i). \quad (19)$$

The compact form of the above relation becomes

$$[\sum_{j=0}^J \sum_{k=0}^m \text{P}_{jk} \mathbf{X} \mathbf{D}(\alpha_{jk}, \beta_{jk})(\mathbf{D}^T)^{kK^{TC}}] \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{G}, \quad (20)$$

The above equation can be written as

$$\mathbf{W}\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{G} \implies [\mathbf{W}; \mathbf{G}], \quad (21)$$

where

$$\mathbf{W} = [\sum_{j=0}^J \sum_{k=0}^m \mathbf{P}_{jk} \mathbf{X} \mathbf{D}(\alpha_{jk}, \beta_{jk})(\mathbf{D}^T)^{kK^{TC}}], \quad (22)$$

and

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_0 & x_0^2 & \dots & x_0^N \\ 1 & x_1 & x_1^2 & \dots & x_1^N \\ 1 & x_2 & x_2^2 & \dots & x_2^N \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_N & x_N^2 & \dots & x_N^N \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{jk} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{P_{jk}(x_0)}{x_0(x_0-c)} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{P_{jk}(x_1)}{x_1(x_1-c)} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \frac{P_{jk}(x_N)}{x_N(x_N-c)} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} g(x_0) \\ g(x_1) \\ g(x_2) \\ \vdots \\ g(x_N) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using the initial condition

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} [a_{ik}\mathbf{X}(0) + c_{ik}\mathbf{X}(c)](\mathbf{D}^T)^{kK^{TC}} = \lambda_i, \quad (23)$$

$$\text{Where } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m-1$$

Matrix form represented as:

$$\mathbf{Z}_i \mathbf{C} = [\lambda] \implies [\mathbf{Z}_i; \lambda_i], \quad (24)$$

where

$$\mathbf{Z} = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} [a_{ik}\mathbf{X}(0) + c_{ik}\mathbf{X}(c)](\mathbf{D}^T)^{kK^{TC}} = [z_{i0} \ z_{i1} \ z_{i2} \ \dots \ z_{iN}].$$

Replace the last $(m-1)$ rows of the matrix $[\mathbf{W}; \mathbf{G}]$ with the matrix \mathbf{Z}_i to obtain the solution under the initial conditions:

$$= \begin{bmatrix} w_{00} & w_{01} & w_{02} & \dots & w_{0N} & ; & g(x_0) \\ w_{10} & w_{11} & w_{12} & \dots & w_{1N} & ; & g(x_1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & ; & \vdots \\ w_{N-m0} & w_{N-m1} & w_{N-m2} & \dots & w_{N-mN} & ; & g(x_{N-m}) \\ z_{00} & z_{01} & z_{02} & \dots & z_{0N} & ; & \lambda_1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & ; & \vdots \\ z_{N-m0} & z_{N-m1} & z_{N-m2} & \dots & z_{N-mN} & ; & \lambda_{m-1} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

If $\text{rank}(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}; \widetilde{\mathbf{G}}) = N+1$, then the coefficient matrix \mathbf{C} is computed by

$$\mathbf{C} = \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}^{-1}; \widetilde{\mathbf{G}}. \quad (26)$$

Numerical Illustration

In this section, we provide examples that serve to illustrate our results and showcase the application.

The singular differential–difference equation is defined as [11]

$$x\mathbf{y}^{(2)}(3x-2) - \frac{2}{(x+1)}\mathbf{y}^{(2)}(x+1) + \mathbf{y}^{(1)}(x-1) - x\mathbf{y}(x) = -57x + 39x^2 - \frac{24x}{x+1} - \frac{4}{x+1} + 19 + 5x^3 - 2x^4, \quad (27)$$

for $0 \leq x \leq 2$ with the initial conditions:

$$y(0) = 1, y^{(1)}(0) = 3. \quad (28)$$

Here:

$$\mathbf{P}_{00}(x) = -x, \mathbf{P}_{10}(x) = 1, \mathbf{P}_{20}(x) = -\frac{2x}{x+1}, \mathbf{P}_{21}(x) = x, \\ \alpha_{00} = 1, \beta_{00} = 0, \\ \alpha_{10} = 1, \beta_{10} = -1, \\ \alpha_{20} = 1, \beta_{20} = 1, \\ \alpha_{21} = 3, \beta_{21} = -2,$$

$$h(x) = 19 - 57x + 39x^2 + 5x^3 - 2x^4 - \frac{24x}{x+1} - \frac{4}{x+1}.$$

The approximate solution $y(x)$ can be obtained by the truncated Laguerre series:

$$y(x) = \sum_{n=0}^N c_n \mathcal{L}_n(x).$$

Numerical Solution for $N = 3$

The collocation points for $b = 2$ and $N = 3$ are computed as:

$$\left\{ x_0 = 0, x_1 = \frac{2}{3}, x_2 = \frac{4}{3}, x_3 = 2 \right\}.$$

The fundamental matrix equation of the problem is:

$$\mathbf{P}_{21}\mathbf{X}\mathbf{B}(\alpha_{21}, \beta_{21})(\mathbf{D}^T)^2\mathbf{K}^{TC} + \mathbf{P}_{20}\mathbf{X}\mathbf{B}(\alpha_{20}, \beta_{20})(\mathbf{D}^T)^2\mathbf{K}^{TC} + \mathbf{P}_{10}\mathbf{X}\mathbf{B}(\alpha_{10}, \beta_{10})\mathbf{D}^T\mathbf{K}^{TC} + \mathbf{P}_{00}\mathbf{X}\mathbf{B}(\alpha_{00}, \beta_{00})\mathbf{K}^{TC} = \mathbf{H}. \quad (29)$$

The matrices are defined as:

$$P_{00} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -2/3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -4/3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$P_{10} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$P_{20} = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -6/5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -6/7 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -2/3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$P_{21} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2/3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 4/3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B(\alpha_{00}, \beta_{00}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B(\alpha_{10}, \beta_{10}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B(\alpha_{20}, \beta_{20}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B(\alpha_{21}, \beta_{21}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -2 & 4 & -8 \\ 0 & 3 & -12 & 36 \\ 0 & 0 & 9 & -54 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 27 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 2/3 & 4/9 & 8/27 \\ 1 & 4/3 & 16/9 & 64/27 \\ 1 & 2 & 4 & 8 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$K^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & -2 & -3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/2 & 3/2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1/6 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} 15 \\ -1019/81 \\ 1381/567155/3 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Substituting the Laguerre coefficients, the approximate solution for $N=3$ is: $y_3(x) = 2x^3 - 5x^2 + 3x + 1$, which matches the exact solution.

Comparison Table of the exact solution and the approximate solutions for $N = 3$ with Bessel collection method is represented as

1 Numerical Results of $N=3$

x_i	Exact solution	BCM(N=3)	LCM (N=3)
0	1	1	1
0.2	1.416	1.416	1.416
0.4	1.528	1.528	1.528
0.6	1.432	1.432	1.432
0.8	1.224	1.224	1.224
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

1 Graphical Representation of Table

From above table and figure it is clear that for $N = 3$ Laguerre Collection Method gives the exact solution.

Conclusion

High-order differential equations, such as linear singular differential-difference equations, are commonly used to simulate physical events and play an essential role in research and engineering. Most of these equations lack an analytical solution, hence numerical approaches may be necessary for approximate solutions. For this reason, the Laguerre collocation approach has been proposed. A significant advantage of the method is that it takes less time to compute and has fewer operations, which reduces cumulative truncation mistakes and improves overall accuracy. As a result, this technique is far faster than the other approaches. Numerical illustrations demonstrated the greater compactness, validity, and accuracy of the Laguerre Collection Method. The Bessel Collection approach has been utilized to compare the numerical outcomes. For varying values of N , the comparison of approaches is shown graphically and in tables. One of the method's many noteworthy benefits is its ease of use in finding approximation answers through computer coding. The computer program MATLAB R2020b has been utilized to compute the numerical illustrations' outcomes. The Appendices contain the codes for the Numerical Illustrations as examples.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declares that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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